

Evaluating Digital Humanities Methods and Tools for the OpenMethods Metablog: An OpenMethods Edit-a-thon

Nunn, Christopher

christopher.nunn@theologie.uni-heidelberg.de
Universität Heidelberg, Deutschland
ORCID: 0000-0001-7208-8636

Horváth, Alíz

aliz.horvath06@gmail.com
Eötvös Loránd University, Ungarn
ORCID: 0000-0002-9131-5504

Wuttke, Ulrike

ulrike.wuttke@fh-potsdam.de
Fachhochschule Potsdam, Deutschland
ORCID: 0000-0002-8217-4025

Introduction

In digitally oriented disciplines, such as the Digital Humanities (DH), the exchange of scholarly information is not confined solely to peer-reviewed journals and academic book series. Instead, it occurs naturally in various online platforms such as blogs, Git repositories, pre-prints, video tutorials, podcasts, social media, and other web 2.0 and 3.0 discourse spaces (AG Digitales Publizieren, 2021). This is particularly crucial when sharing critical reflections and expertise related to tools and methodologies (König, 2015).

The DARIAH-EU-sustained OpenMethods metablog aims to explore and deliver solutions for the rich and dynamically evolving DH scene that challenges the traditional formats of scholarly communication that is deeply rooted in print culture. It offers a comprehensive platform for consolidating diverse forms of open access content in multiple languages, specifically focusing on methods and tools within the field of DH. It provides a convenient way for DH experts from around the globe to select, propose, curate, highlight and evaluate open access content. It disseminates knowledge and enhances the recognition of DH methods and tools among peers and embraces a broad range of publication formats, aiming for inclusivity by acknowledging content types that often go unnoticed in formal research evaluation and conventional research papers and book chapters (Eve, 2020, Neuber und Sahle, 2022).

The OpenMethods metablog approach means that its Editorial Team is actively involved in the selection and curation of published content. The content is proposed by the OpenMethods Editorial Team members themselves as well as by community volunteers (Engelhardt et al., 2017). Additionally, the nomination of content is open to anyone, either through social media or through the nomination tool on the OpenMethods platform. External collaborators, including students studying DH, are especially encouraged to contribute and be recognized on the OpenMethods website. After the process of commenting on, filtering, and curating the nominations based on the established evaluation criteria, successful entries not only get republished on the platform, but also get categorized using the Taxonomy of Digital Research Activities in the Arts and Humanities (TaDiRAH) developed by Borek et al. (2016; 2021). Additionally, a brief introduction in English is provided by one of the Editorial Team members, explaining the significance and relevance of the contribution.

OpenMethods aims to ensure a wide range of coverage in various languages. The Editorial Team has deliberately chosen an interdisciplinary and multilingual approach with the goal of showcasing the diversity of DH discussions within different regional, national, and language communities (Del Rio Rande et al., 2018). Moreover, OpenMethods aims not only to enhance the representation of traditionally marginalized languages and actors, such as female tool-makers in the Digital Humanities and a particular focus on non-Anglophone, under-resourced languages (such as those with non-Latin scripts), but to also ensure that the content selected handles various topics, including method and tool descriptions, critical evaluations of tools and methods, and both practical and theoretical reflections on the digital conduct of humanities research. This is done to explore how the growing influence of digital methods and tools is reshaping scholarly attitudes and scientific practices within humanities research. This objective holds significance both for the OpenMethods platform specifically and for the broader discourse in the field of Digital Humanities, as highlighted by Horvath (2021) and related research.

Recognizing the vast and dynamic nature of born-digital scholarly discourse spaces, there is a need to establish mechanisms for filtering and building trust in the openly accessible content within them (Eve, 2020; Fitzpatrick, 2011; Nyhan, 2020). This requirement has been addressed by OpenMethods, a platform that leverages the expertise of the scholarly community to establish such filtering and trust-building mechanisms. During the OpenMethods Edit-a-Thon at DH Graz (Tóth-Czifra et al., 2023) a vivid discussion arose around the selection and evaluation process that showed the necessity to further develop the scope of the metablog's selection and the direction of the evaluation process to meet inclusivity and diversity criteria.

Goals of the Workshop

In this workshop, we invite scholars in the arts and humanities, regardless of their career stage or disciplinary and geographical backgrounds, to explore the OpenMethods metablog as an innovative platform for publication.

Nominated papers for the OpenMethods metablog are reviewed according to seven different evaluation criteria: scope, openness, relevance, clarity, diversity, language, as well as assessment and validation. During the workshop, each of these criteria will be considered and discussed in more detail. For example, should contributions only be considered if they are in formats without peer review like blogposts or podcasts? Should the preparation of an introduction by the editors follow certain guidelines in order to increase its quality and thus also gain value for their own publication list (Neuber und Sahle, 2022)? Under specific circumstances, could reports of research results without explicit method or tool criticism also be considered? Given the development of the computational humanities (Piotrowski, 2020), should it be possible to nominate papers that are aimed exclusively at a technically literate audience? How can or should a metablog do justice to diversity in the sense of uncovering data biases and hidden hierarchies in working processes (D'Ignazio und Klein, 2020)? Is multilingualism justified and timely, or is it even more inclusive to focus on a few dominant languages and use more and more improved translation software?

One of the main goals of the workshop is to revisit the OpenMethods metablog evaluation criteria through an interactive conceptual discussion with the workshop participants. The discussion will be followed by a hands-on phase: selecting and evaluating nominations and writing introductions. Ultimately the engagement of the participants with the metablog will serve to foster sustainability through reuse and community building by involving participants in the editorial process and enticing them to spread the word and join the team.

Workshop Outline

The workshop is designed as a half-day event (4 hours) consisting of an in-depth critical discussion of the review criteria and a hands-on writing phase.

The format will be an edit-a-thon, with a major focus on interactive discussion, as well as a hands-on writing phase after an introductory presentation on OpenMethods as a platform, its goals and the evaluation criteria.

Structure of the workshop (total 240 min):

Introduction and Q&A (30 min)

Introduction to the evaluation criteria and discussion (30 min)

Nomination phase (suggestion key topical areas: non-English content) (30 min)

BREAK (15 min)

Self-Evaluation (Checkbox exercise) (30 min)

Deliberation phase (15 min)

Groups formation and choosing of content to collaboratively write introductions (15 min)

Break (15 min)

Hands-On Writing Phase (50 min.)

Wrap-up, takeaways, reflections (10 min)

Target Audience and Participant Number

The intended target group is people with an interest in the topic of the workshop. There are no prerequisites for participation. The main language of the workshop presentations will be English, German contributions to the discussions are welcomed. Nominations are encouraged in any language.

For the hands-on part, each participant should bring a computer or tablet.

Group size: 20 participants.

Required Technical Equipment

For technical equipment, a projector is required. Due to the interactive nature of the workshop, online participation will unfortunately not be feasible.

Furthermore, the following equipment will be required: whiteboard or flipchart.

Facilitators and Research Interests

Alíz Horváth has a PhD in East Asian Languages and Civilizations from the University of Chicago and currently works as assistant professor of East Asian History and Digital Humanities at Eötvös Loránd University (Hungary). She is a member of the core editorial team of OpenMethods since 2020 and has been a contributor to the pioneering project New Languages for NLP, organized by Princeton. She is also founder and co-chair of the DARIAH-EU Multilingual DH Working Group.

Christopher Nunn is Postdoc at Heidelberg University. He has a PhD in Church History (Ancient Christianity) and founded the Interdisciplinary Forum of Digital Textual Studies (InFoDiTex) as well as the TheoLab, a research network for computational theology at Heidelberg University. He is a member of the OpenMethods Editorial Team since 2019. His research interests are in community building and science communication among others.

Ulrike Wuttke has been the Deputy Chief Editor since the launch of OpenMethods in 2017. She has a PhD in Medieval Dutch Literature from Ghent University (Belgium) and currently is professor of Library Science at University of Applied Sciences Potsdam. Her research interests include scholarly communication and Open Science. Among others she is a member of the editorial board of the Zeitschrift für Digitale Geisteswissenschaften (ZfDG).

Acknowledgments: OpenMethods was initiated during the Horizon 2020 project Humanities at Scale (2020). It has since then been sustained by DARIAH-EU (Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities). DARIAH's approach to supporting and strengthening the Digital Humanities entails validation of Data Services and tools, building networks of people, providing training and education opportunities, enabling transnational and transdisciplinary approaches across Europe.

Bibliographie

- AG Digitales Publizieren.** 2021. Digitales Publizieren in den Geisteswissenschaften: Begriffe, Standards, Empfehlungen (= Zeitschrift für digitale Geisteswissenschaften / Working Papers, 1). *Zeitschrift für Digitale Geisteswissenschaften*. https://doi.org/10.17175/wp_2021_001 (zugegriffen: 18. Juli 2023).
- Borek, Luise, Quinn Dombrowski, Jody Perkins und Christof Schöch.** 2016. "TaDiRAH: A Case Study in Pragmatic Classification." *DHQ* 10, Nr. 1. <http://www.digitalhumanities.org/dhq/vol/10/1/000235/000235.html> (zugegriffen: 18. Juli 2023).
- Borek, Luise, Canan Hastik, Vera Khramova, Klaus Illmayer und Jonathan D. Geiger.** 2021. "TaDiRAH Revised, Formalized and FAIR", In *Information between Data and Knowledge*. Information Science and its Neighbors from Data Science to Digital Humanities - Proceedings of the 16th International Symposium of Information Science (ISI 2021), Regensburg, Germany, 8th - 10th March 2021 (=Schriften zur Informationswissenschaft 74), hg. von Thomas Schmidt und Christian Wolff, 321-332. Glückstadt: Hülsbusch. <https://epub.uni-regensburg.de/44951/> (zugegriffen: 18. Juli 2023).
- D'Ignazio, Catherine und Lauren F. Klein.** 2020. *Data Feminism*. Cambridge (Mass.), London: The MIT Press.
- Engelhardt, Claudia, Claudio Leone, Nicolas Larrousse, Delphine Montoliu, Yoann Moranville, Pierre Mounier, Jenny Oltersdorf, Paulin Ribbe und Ulrike Wuttke.** 2017. *Open Humanities Methods Review Journal (Research Report)*. DARIAH; TGIR Huma-Num (UMS3598); Göttingen State and University Library. <https://hal.archives-ouvertes.fr/hal-01685852> (zugegriffen: 18. Juli 2023).
- Eve, Martin Paul.** 2020. Violins in the Subway: Scarcity Correlations, Evaluative Cultures, and Disciplinary Authority in the Digital Humanities. In *Digital Technology and the Practices of Humanities Research*, hg. von Jennifer Edmond, 103-122. Cambridge, United Kingdom: Open Book Publishers. <https://doi.org/10.11647/OBP.0192> (zugegriffen: 18. Juli 2023).
- Fitzpatrick, Kathleen.** 2011. *Planned Obsolescence: Publishing, Technology, and the Future of the Academy*. New York: New York University Press.
- Horváth, Alíz.** 2021. "Enhancing Language Inclusivity in Digital Humanities: Towards Sensitivity and Multilingualism: Includes interviews with Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra and Cosima Wagner". In *Modern Languages Open* 1, <http://doi.org/10.3828/mlo.v0i0.382> (zugegriffen: 18. Juli 2023).
- König, Mareike.** 2015. Herausforderung für unsere Wissenschaftskultur: Weblogs in den Geisteswissenschaften. In *Digital Humanities. Praktiken der Digitalisierung, der Dissemination und der Selbstreflexivität*, hg. von Wolfgang Schmale, 91:57-74. Historische Mitteilungen – Beihefte. Franz Steiner Verlag. <https://doi.org/10.25162/9783515111508> (zugegriffen: 18. Juli 2023).
- Neuber, Frederike und Patrick Sahle.** 2022. "Nach den Büchern: Rezensionen digitaler Forschungsressourcen". *H-Soz-Kult* (Forum: Rez.). www.hsozkult.de/debate/id/fddebate-132457 (zugegriffen: 18. Juli 2023).
- Nyhan, Julianne.** 2020. "7. The Evaluation and Peer Review of Digital Scholarship in the Humanities: Experiences, Discussions, and Histories". In *Digital Technology and the Practices of Humanities Research*, hg. von Jennifer Edmond, 163-82. Open Book Publishers. <https://doi.org/10.11647/obp.0192.07> (zugegriffen: 18. Juli 2023).
- Piotrowski, Michael.** 2020. „Ain't no way around it: Why we need to be clear about what we mean by 'Digital Humanities'". SocArXiv. <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/d2kb6> (zugegriffen: 18.07.2023).
- Del Rio Riande, Gimena, Gabriel Calarco, Gabriela Striker und Romina De León.** 2018. *Humanidades Digitales: Construcciones locales en contextos globales*. Buenos Aires: Universidad de Buenos Aires. http://eprints.rclis.org/32718/1/Actas_Humanidades%20Digitales_Construcciones%20locales%20en%20contextos%20Globales_all.pdf (zugegriffen: 18. Juli 2023).
- Tóth-Czifra, Erzsébet, Ulrike Wuttke, Alíz Horváth und Christopher Nunn.** 2023. Amplifying unheard voices in Digital Humanities: an OpenMethods edit-a-thon. In *Digital Humanities 2023: Book of Abstracts*. Digital Humanities 2023. Collaboration as Opportunity. (DH2023), Graz, Austria, hg. von Anne Baillot, Toma Tasovac, Walter Scholger, und Georg Vogeler, 26-27. Graz: Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7961822> (zugegriffen: 18. Juli 2023).